

EVORoads

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Project deliverable D6.2

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

TABLE OF CONTENTS	3
LIST OF FIGURES	4
LIST OF TABLES	5
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS	6
PROJECT EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
DELIVERABLE EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	8
1 INTRODUCTION	9
1.1 MAPPING EVORADS OUTPUTS	9
1.2 DELIVERABLE OVERVIEW AND REPORT STRUCTURE	10
1.3 PROGRESS SINCE THE FIRST DELIVERABLE VERSION	10
2 APPROACH TO THE DMP	11
3 DATA AND ETHICS MANAGEMENT	12
3.1 DATA CATALOGUE AND THE EVORADSDCAT-AP METADATA PROFILE	12
3.2 EVORADS DMP METADATA PROFILE	15
3.2.1 <i>GENERAL INFORMATION AND DATA SUMMARY</i>	15
3.2.1 <i>FAIR DATA</i>	17
3.2.2 <i>ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES</i>	20
3.2.3 <i>DATA SECURITY</i>	20
3.2.4 <i>ETHICAL ASPECTS</i>	21
3.2.5 <i>OTHER ISSUES</i>	22
3.3 HOW THE DATA CATALOGUE SUPPORTS THE DMP	22
4 ETHICS COMPLIANCE: AI-ACT	25
5 CONCLUSIONS	27
6 REFERENCES	28
7 ANNEX	29
ANNEX I – COLLECTED DATASETS	29

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LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: EvoRoads metadata profile on the Argos platform	11
Figure 2: Conceptual steps followed in the definition of the EvoRoadsDCAT-AP metadata profile	13
Figure 3: Flowchart showing the appropriate steps to follow for a correct usage of data sources in the project	23

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LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Adherence to EvoRoads GA Deliverables & Tasks Description	9
Table 2: Description of a Dataset according to the EvoRoadsDCAT-AP metadata profile	14
Table 3: Description of a Distribution according to the EvoRoadsDCAT-AP metadata profile	15
Table 4: “General Information and Data Summary” section of the EvoRoads metadata profile	16
Table 5: “FAIR DATA – Making data Findable” section of the EvoRoads metadata profile	18
Table 6: “FAIR DATA – Making data openly accessible” section of the EvoRoads metadata profile	18
Table 7: “FAIR DATA – Making interoperable” section of the EvoRoads metadata profile	19
Table 8: “FAIR DATA – Increase data re-use” section of the EvoRoads metadata profile	19
Table 9: “Allocation of resources” section of the EvoRoads metadata profile	20
Table 10: “Data security” section of the EvoRoads metadata profile	21
Table 11: “Ethical Aspects” section of the EvoRoads metadata profile	22
Table 12: “Other Aspects” section of the EvoRoads metadata profile	22

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Acronym	Meaning
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
KoM	Kick-off Meeting
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LC	Lead Contact
ODI	Open Data Institute
STC	Scientific and Technical Committee
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
WP	Work Package
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary
AI	Artificial Intelligence
DCAT-AP	Data Catalog Vocabulary Application Profile
API	Application Programming Interface
NAP	National Access Point

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PROJECT EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The EC-funded project EvoRoads (Evolutionary Solutions for Realising a Holistic Safe System Approach for All Road Users) is committed to advancing the European Union's VisionZero initiative by implementing a comprehensive framework that integrates innovative models, tools, and services for data-driven safety assessments.

The project focuses on developing of a connectivity platform that digitalises transport infrastructure assets while enabling the seamless integration of safety assessment services. By leveraging advanced artificial intelligence, EvoRoads analyses infrastructure monitoring data at various geospatial levels, enabling proactive risk warnings and supporting road operators in managing maintenance more effectively, enhancing safety and operational efficiency. It also defines safety criteria and quantification methods for key performance indicators (KPIs) to monitor safety performance as part of the "Safe System" approach.

The results are developed alongside five axes: (1) an Evolutionary Safety Assessment Framework setting the basis by defining how to measure road safety in a multilayered catalogue; (2) a Road Asset & Safety Management Digital Twin collecting and distributing safety data; (3) Advanced Monitoring Safety Systems that leverage data to provide infrastructure owners with clear insights into the safety levels of their roads; (4) Proactive Safety Warning Systems ensuring that critical safety issues are raised pro-actively and in real-time to prevent safety hazards; and finally, all these results are combined in (5) Solutions Integration, Augmentation and Impact Assessment tools and products allowing for take-up of the results in the wider market. These axes converge into a Safe Mobility Data Space where all data related to EvoRoads' safety criteria and solutions are combined.

EvoRoads' methodologies and technologies will be validated in four Living Labs (LLs) addressing diverse road user scenarios across urban and rural environments to ensure broad applicability and effectiveness. EvoRoads LLs are situated in Spain (focusing on Hazard-aware assets for better infrastructure safety level for existing and future roads users), Italy (focusing on Dynamic Road infrastructure safety diagnosis enhanced by emerging vehicle and digital technologies), Latvia (focusing on Automated (advanced) low-cost infrastructure monitoring and diagnostics: road hot spots, bridges, tunnels), and Romania (focusing on Remote sensing and warning technologies for better infrastructure and road conditions).

The EvoRoads project runs from May 2024 until April 2027. A scale-up event is foreseen towards the end of the project to allow for the wider market to consider EvoRoads' results and to help provide ways forward.

Social Media link:

For further information please visit evoroads-project.eu

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DELIVERABLE EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This is the second version of D6.2 “Data Management Plan (DMP)” of the EvoRoads project. The DMP describes how data will be collected, stored, accessed, exchanged, made interoperable, and re-used. The DMP addresses the full data management approach for making research data FAIR (i.e., Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). Through the definition and adoption of a comprehensive metadata profile, the DMP provides information on the control of research data, and how data will be handled and stored throughout the project’s lifetime and beyond. Particular attention will be given to ethical issues dealing with the right to data protection and the management of sensitive data.

D6.2 outlines how datasets generated and collected will be documented using two newly developed and complementary metadata profiles: the EvoRoadsDCAT-AP (Data Catalog Vocabulary-Application Profile) profile for simplifying data sharing in internal project activities, and the EvoRoads DMP profile for the description of EvoRoads’s datasets in published deliverables at scheduled milestones (M8, M18, M36). The current release (second version) details data management practices, software tools employed, and metadata frameworks adopted.

Since the first version of the deliverable, the Argos platform has been adopted as the core technical solution for developing the EvoRoads Data Management Plan (DMP). The metadata framework has evolved into two complementary profiles: the EvoRoads DMP metadata profile, used for DMP authoring, and the EvoRoads DCAT-AP metadata profile, used to describe data sources in the project’s internal data catalogue. While the data catalogue supports the daily internal management and sharing of datasets, the DMP serves a broader, periodic documentation purpose. It is published at key milestones (M8, M18, M36) to provide a comprehensive overview of the project’s data assets at those points in time. Beyond internal coordination, the DMP is also designed to facilitate data discovery and reuse by external stakeholders, including researchers and similar projects, thereby enhancing the project’s transparency and impact.

The data management approach ensures that ethical compliance is considered throughout the data lifecycle. All data sources, whether reused or newly generated, must comply with the EU ethical and data privacy requirements. Partners are supported in this process by the European Commission’s ethical decision tree tool, which helps determine whether a dataset involves personal data or raises ethical concerns. Any identified issues are reviewed by the Ethics and Data Management Team, who may recommend mitigation measures such as anonymisation or data minimisation. If concerns cannot be resolved, the dataset is excluded from the project. Once these criteria are met, data can be described using the EvoRoads DCAT-AP profile and submitted to the catalogue for review and publication.

A dedicated section has also been added to the DMP to describe how the project guarantees the ethical use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in alignment with the EU AI Act. Finally, the list of datasets has been revised to remove those no longer relevant and include newly identified ones, as detailed in the Annex I.

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CHOOSE AN ITEM.

1 INTRODUCTION

The presented document consists of Deliverable D6.2 “Data Management Plan” which has been developed under WP6, “Project Management,” Task 6.4, “Responsible Innovation: Ethics Open Access and Data Management.”

The Data Management Plan (DMP) aims to introduce the essential aspects of the project's data management policy. It aims to provide a strategy for managing data generated and collected during the project and optimising access to and re-use of research data.

Each dataset used in EvoRoads will be described according to two different metadata profiles. Initially, when the data is being used for the internal project activities, the dataset will be described according to the newly developed EvoRoadsDCAT-AP metadata profile. The same data is going to be described according to the EvoRoads DMP metadata profile when included in the DMP to be published at specific points in time (M8, M18, M36).

The second release of D6.2 describes how data is managed in the EvoRoads project, what software tools are used for the data management and what metadata profiles are being used to describe the handled data.

The DMP details which data the EvoRoads project will manage and generate, how they will be exploited or made accessible for verification purposes and re-use, and how they will be preserved and curated. The DMP addresses the full data management approach. As part of making research data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. The DMP includes information on:

- the control of research data, both during and after the conclusion of the project.
- what type of information will be gathered, analysed or produced.
- which framework and guidelines will be used.
- whether data will be accessible to the public.
- how data will be handled and stored throughout the project's lifetime and beyond.

As the DMP is meant to be a living document, D6.2 will receive a final update at M36.

1.1 MAPPING EVOROADS OUTPUTS

This section provides a mapping of EvoRoads Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1: Adherence to EvoRoads GA Deliverables & Tasks Description

EVOROADS GA COMPONENT TITLE	EVOROADS GA COMPONENT OUTLINE	RESPECTIVE DOCUMENT CHAPTER(S)	JUSTIFICATION
DELIVERABLE			
D6.2 Data Management Plan	Data Management Plan: how data will be collected, stored, accessed, exchanged, and made interoperable, as well as how data approved for	Chapters 2, 3	Chapter 2 contains a description of the decisions that lead to the adoption of the Argos platform for the DMP. Chapter 3 contains a description of the approach

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EVORoads GA COMPONENT TITLE	EVORoads GA COMPONENT OUTLINE	RESPECTIVE DOCUMENT CHAPTER(S)	JUSTIFICATION
	publication can be used by others.		to data management in the EvoRoads project with a focus on the adopted EvoRoadsDCAT-AP and EvoRoads DMP metadata profiles.

TASKS

T6.4 Responsible Innovation: Ethics, Open Access and Data Management	Task 6.4 aims to monitor various activities within the project to ensure sensible developments at the ethical, open access and data management level, referred to as Responsible Research Innovation (RRI). Among them there are data ethics and data management.	Chapter 3, 4	Chapter 3 outlines the methodology used for data and ethics management within the EvoRoads project. Chapter 4 outlines how the project ensures compliance with the AI-ACT ethical requirements.
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1.2 DELIVERABLE OVERVIEW AND REPORT STRUCTURE

The document is divided into the following sections:

- Chapter 2 describes how the DMP metadata profile described in the first version of the D6.2 is going to be used for the this second and third releases of the DMP. Additionally, the process through which the Argos platform has been chosen as the publishing portal for the DMP is described.
- Chapter 3 outlines the data management approach of the EvoRoads Project. It describes the data lifecycle between the data catalogue and the DMP, detailing the two metadata profiles developed for these tools: the EvoRoadsDCAT-AP profile for the catalogue and the EvoRoads DMP profile for the DMP.
- Chapter 4 describes how the EvoRoads project intends to guarantee compliance with the European AI-ACT and thus satisfy its ethical requirements.

1.3 PROGRESS SINCE THE FIRST DELIVERABLE VERSION

Since the first version of the deliverable, the Argos platform has been adopted as the technical solution for authoring the DMP. The metadata profile originally introduced to describe data sources has been renamed as the EvoRoads DMP metadata profile, reflecting the introduction of an additional profile, the EvoRoadsDCAT-AP metadata profile, which is specifically used to describe data sources in the project’s data catalogue. Additionally, a chapter was added to describe how the ethical usage of Artificial Intelligence (AI) systems is guaranteed in the project by conforming to the AI ACT [5]. Furthermore, several datasets included in the initial version of the DMP were later deemed not useful for the project, while additional datasets have since been identified as relevant. These changes are reflected in the list of datasets available in the Annex I.

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2 APPROACH TO THE DMP

To effectively manage datasets to be reported in the Data Management Plan, we defined and introduced a dedicated metadata profile, initially named “EvoRoads metadata profile”, as described in the first version of the D6.2. This profile was designed to cover the necessary information required by the Data Management Plan template¹ provided by the European Union. For the second release of the DMP, the profile has remained unchanged in substance but has undergone a change in naming. With the introduction of another metadata profile – the EvoRoadsDCAT-AP metadata profile, used in the project’s data catalogue – the original “EvoRoads metadata profile” was renamed to the “EvoRoads DMP metadata profile” to avoid confusion. The EvoRoads DMP metadata profile is described in its entirety in Chapter 3.2.

In addition to defining the profile, another consideration was the choice of technological solution for writing, managing, publishing and releasing the DMP. The evaluated choices have been DMPonline², the Argos³ platform, and Cefriel’s KCONG⁴ catalogue. The main advantages and disadvantages of these platforms have been listed in the first version of D6.2 and as intended, Argos has been chosen as the most suitable option for the EvoRoads project. The EvoRoads DMP metadata profile was submitted to the Argos technical team for validation, including the definition of fixed values for certain fields to simplify dataset submission. The team confirmed successful integration of the profile, allowing it to leverage Argos’ built-in functionalities such as automatically linking researcher names to their ORCID profiles via ORCID IDs, thereby streamlining metadata entry.

The EvoRoads DMP metadata profile is now publicly available on the Argos platform (Figure 1) and will be used for both this second and third release of the DMP. The DMP for the second release has already been published on the Argos platform, while an export of all the described datasets used in the project is provided in the Annex I.

Name ↕	Type ▼	Language ▼	Updated ▾	Preview	Select
AQUASERV template	Dataset	English	11/7/25, 4:30 PM		Select
AQUASERV all categories generic template	Dataset	English	24/3/25, 5:03 PM		Select
AQUASERV Molecular Biology & Omics sequencing	Dataset	English	24/3/25, 3:46 PM		Select
EvoRoads Template	Dataset	English	20/3/25, 11:36 AM		Select
CHISTERA Data Management	Dataset	English	27/9/24, 2:19 AM		Select

Figure 1: EvoRoads metadata profile on the Argos platform

1 https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/temp-form/report/data-management-plan_he_en.docx

2 <https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/>

3 <https://argos.openaire.eu/hom>

4 <https://kcong.cefrirel.com/>

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3 DATA AND ETHICS MANAGEMENT

To address the data requirements of the project and to implement an effective data management strategy, two principal entities have been established: (1) a data catalogue, in which the datasets intended for use within the project are documented; and (2) the DMP. Although their functions differ, these entities partially overlap in the information they contain.

3.1 DATA CATALOGUE AND THE EVOROADSDCAT-AP METADATA PROFILE

The data catalogue is designed as an internal project tool to support the practical activities carried out across the project's various tasks and partners. Accordingly, datasets are documented with reference to their prospective internal use and must be described by a metadata profile that satisfies both the specific requirements of the project and the broader standards of the mobility data domain. As an example of such activities, data sources described in the data catalogue can be accessed and reused by other technical partners, while partners such as the Ethical and Data Management team can check the data source for data privacy and ethical compliance. To achieve this goal, the EvoRoadsDCAT-AP metadata profile has been developed and used for the project's data catalogue.

EvoRoadsDCAT-AP is an extension of the existing MobilityDCAT-AP [6] metadata specification, developed within the NAPCORE initiative. MobilityDCAT-AP builds on the widely adopted DCAT-AP standard to harmonize metadata across European National Access Points (NAPs) and mobility platforms. It enhances dataset discoverability, promotes semantic interoperability, and supports the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). By providing clear, platform-independent metadata descriptions in human and machine-readable formats, it enables seamless integration with third-party systems for example, through API based import and export. MobilityDCAT-AP defines precise fields for key aspects such as data topic, provider, and geographical coverage, following Semantic Web best practices to ensure interoperability with existing specifications. To better understand its foundations, it is important to first look at DCAT and its specialized profile, DCAT-AP.

The Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT) is an RDF vocabulary that standardises the description of data catalogues through a defined set of classes and properties. Central to DCAT are the classes *Dataset* and *Distribution*: A *Dataset* represents a coherent collection of data, while a *Distribution* refers to a specific physical embodiment of that dataset, such as a file, API, or service endpoint. For instance, a dataset on public transport routes may have one distribution as a CSV file and another as a GeoJSON file, both describing the same data but in different formats.

Building on this foundation, the DCAT Application Profile (DCAT-AP) specifies a profile for European data portals to enable aggregation, exchange, search, and automated processing of metadata. While relying on DCAT concepts, DCAT-AP refines their application by defining cardinalities and obligations (mandatory, recommended, optional), recommending controlled vocabularies, and introducing additional properties for specific metadata fields.

To ensure consistency, public guidelines define how DCAT-AP may be extended. Extensions must remain compatible with the base profile, allowing DCAT-AP compliant metadata to be extracted. Extensions either provide further recommendations on the use of classes and properties or broaden the scope of the profile. Such modifications may involve adjusting cardinalities and obligations, prescribing controlled vocabularies, or adding new properties for metadata.

EvoRoadsDCAT-AP has been established as an extension of mobilityDCAT-AP to preserve interoperability with data platform already using this profile, but also to address specific data requirements identified together with project partners following the steps shown in Figure 2. For instance, during a research project it is frequently uncertain where a dataset is

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being used, or whether it remains in active use. To mitigate this issue, the profile has been extended with two specific metadata fields, *Work Package (WP)* and *Workstream*, which enable tracking of the work package and task in which each dataset is used. Similarly, to facilitate data reuse within the internal context of the project, a new field has been introduced to summarise the specific EvoRoads data requirement that each dataset may satisfy (e.g., *Vehicle Sensor Data*). This information is captured in the metadata profile through the dedicated *Data Requirements* field.

Figure 2: Conceptual steps followed in the definition of the EvoRoadsDCAT-AP metadata profile

On the same note, to support the assessment of whether a dataset can be reused in contexts comparable to its current application, the profile includes the field *Usage of the Data in the Project*. This field contains a description of the overall activities in which the dataset is involved, with details on tasks and deliverables where applicable. Another important aspect that emerged during the requirements analysis concerns the treatment of generated data. It is essential to distinguish whether a dataset has been created entirely from scratch or derived through the refinement or enrichment of an existing dataset. To capture this information, the metadata profile has been extended with the field *Reused Data*. In a similar manner, documenting the processes and techniques applied in dataset creation is of particular importance, as it may be necessary to indicate, for example, that anonymisation procedures were employed to handle sensitive data or that the dataset complies with specific regulatory frameworks. For this purpose, the profile has been further enriched with the field *Data Creation Process*. Finally, it is necessary to determine whether a dataset may raise ethical concerns either in its creation or in its use. Attention must be given to potential ethical or legal issues that could affect the conditions under which the data can be shared. To keep track of this aspect, the *Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing* field has been added.

Since mobilityDCAT-AP already defines metadata fields for describing data sources in the mobility domain, it has been extended with EvoRoads-specific fields to better address the needs of this project. The resulting EvoRoadsDCAT-AP metadata profile builds on existing structures, reusing the *dcats:Dataset* class shown in Table 2 and the *dcats:Distribution* class shown in Table 3 below. For each field, the profile specifies both the intended semantic meaning and the corresponding cardinality constraints.

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Table 2: Description of a Dataset according to the EvoRoadsDCAT-AP metadata profile

DATASET		
FIELD	DESCRIPTION	CARDINALITY CONSTRAINTS
Dataset id	A unique dataset number will be assigned by Cefriel after the initial data collection phase	1
Dataset name	Name of the dataset	1
Description	Description of dataset	1
Dataset Status	Status of the integration of the dataset in the project	1
Category (Type of output)	Basic categorization of the dataset	1..n
Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)	What project data requirements the dataset addresses	1..n
Partner responsible for the data source	Full name(s) of researcher(s) with affiliation (company or institution name) and email contact info responsible for the dataset inside of the project	1..n
Work packages	In what work package(s) will this data be involved?	1..n
Workstream	In what tasks will this data be involved?	1..n
Usage of the data in the project	A description of the overall activities that should involve the specific dataset, with details on task and deliverables, where possible.	0..1
Related safety KPI(s)	What project safety KPI(s) the dataset addresses. The safety KPI(s) are described in D1.1	0..n
Geographical coverage	Spatial area covered by the data. It may be a location such as "Madrid" or a collection of coordinates	1..n
Temporal coverage start	Starting datetime of the span of time covered by the dataset, for example the dataset may contain data from 2023 to 2024	0..1 (RECOMMENDED)
Temporal coverage end	Ending datetime of the span of time covered by the dataset, for example the dataset may contain data from 2023 to 2024	0..1 (RECOMMENDED)
Update frequency	How often the dataset is updated in seconds	1
Dataset licence	Specify here the type of data licence considered	1
Dataset metadata licence	License for the metadata of the data distribution	1
Reused data	Provide the source of reused data. If available, include a link to a platform like Zenodo or a webpage. If the data isn't public, add a brief description	0..1
Data creation process [generated data only]	How the dataset is generated. For example, data might be collected from sensors from a particular case study, and the collected data then needs to be anonymised through anonymisation techniques	1
Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing	Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? Potential issues can be identified using the ethics data protection decision tree (https://ec.europa.eu/assets/rtd/ethics-data-protection-decision-tree/index.html)	0..1

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Table 3: Description of a Distribution according to the EvoRoadsDCAT-AP metadata profile

DISTRIBUTION		
Field	Description	Cardinality constraints
Data Standard	Data standard followed by the data distribution	1
Format of the data	Format of the data distribution	1
Size	Estimated size of the dataset in bytes	1
Data sample	If available, a sample of the data for this dataset	0..1 (RECOMMENDED)
Download URL	Direct download URL	0..1
Access URL	URL used to access the data such as the link to the data portal where the data is stored, may be the same as the direct download link	1
Application layer protocol	Protocol used to access data	1
Communication Method	Interaction method to retrieve the data	1

While the DMP is implemented through the Argos platform, the data catalogue will be implemented through a CKAN⁵ based data portal. As this implementation could not be made available prior to the second release of the DMP (M18), an interim solution was introduced to collect the description of data sources. For this purpose, an Excel file structured according to the EvoRoadsDCAT-AP metadata profile was shared among project partners, enabling the revision of data sources identified in the initial release of the DMP as well as the incorporation of additional sources recently employed in the project.

3.2 EVOROADS DMP METADATA PROFILE

This section describes the metadata profile defined and adopted in EvoRoads to describe data sources in the DMP, supporting the management of data generated and collected during the project, and optimising access to and re-use of research data.

A reference table has been defined to collect this metadata, and it is described in the following paragraphs according to the identified sections: general information, data summary, FAIR data, other research outputs, allocation of resources, ethical aspects, and other issues.

3.2.1 GENERAL INFORMATION AND DATA SUMMARY

This section provides an overview of the section of the EvoRoads metadata profile (see Table 2) used to collect general information about each dataset, including its identification, relation to the project, and data summary.

⁵ <https://www.ckan.org/>

The first part of the information collected requires a dataset ID, which is assigned by EvoRoads after the initial data collection phase, a name to identify the dataset, a description of the dataset, and the partners responsible for collecting and managing the data (researcher’s name). Moreover, it collects information on the category the dataset belongs to (e.g., Vulnerable Road User (VRU), Vehicle, Safety, Traffic, Infrastructure, Connectivity) and the data requirements it fulfils (e.g., road user behavior, driving behavior, road traffic, road defects).

The section “Relation to the project” supports the specification of the workstream (detailed at the task level) and the WPs in which the described dataset is involved.

The third part of the information collected provides a summary of the dataset, including fields such as the purpose of the data, its schema and format, size, the license for the metadata describing the dataset, and the type of license considered. Moreover, it defines where the data is stored and the value of the dataset both from the project’s perspective and beyond the project’s lifetime.

A distinction is made between re-used datasets, for which the source of the re-used data is required, and generated datasets, for which the data generation process needs to be specified.

Finally, information on available data samples and the reference to project safety KPI(s) the dataset addresses are provided.

The fields are described in Table 4.

Table 4: “General Information and Data Summary” section of the EvoRoads metadata profile

DATASET ID	<i>CEFRIEL WILL ASSIGN A UNIQUE DATASET NUMBER AFTER THE INITIAL DATA COLLECTION PHASE.</i>
DATASET name	<name>
Description	<i>Description of the dataset</i>
Category (Type of output)	<i>Basic categorization</i>
Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)	<i>What project data requirements the dataset address</i>
Partners	<i>Full name(s) of the researcher(s) responsible for the data within the project</i>
RELATION TO THE PROJECT	
Workstream	<i>Tx.y, Tz.k</i>
Work packages	<i>What work packages will use/intend to use this dataset WP x, WP y</i>
DATA SUMMARY	
Purpose of the data	<i>A description of the overall activities involving the specific dataset is expected. This should include detailed information on tasks and deliverables whenever possible.</i>
Schema of the data	<i>Schema of the data. Examples: GTFS, SIRI ...</i>
Format of the data	<i>Format of the data Examples: CSV, XML ...</i>

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DATASET ID	<i>CEFRIEL WILL ASSIGN A UNIQUE DATASET NUMBER AFTER THE INITIAL DATA COLLECTION PHASE.</i>
Size	<i>Estimated size of the dataset</i>
Dataset metadata license	<i>License for the metadata that describes the dataset. In most cases, this value will be the same as the dataset license.</i>
Data license	<i>Specify here the type of data license considered. For example, open license, oDbI ...</i>
Data storage	<i>Where the data are stored</i>
Data value (long term)	<i>The expected value for the dataset, both from the project point of view and after the project lifetime (if any)</i>
Re-used data	<i>Origin of the data that is being re-used. If possible, there should be a link to a platform like Zenodo where the data has been published. Otherwise, a link to a webpage would be enough. If the re-used data is not publicly available, then a textual description of the data should be inserted.</i>
Data creation process (only for generated data)	<i>How the dataset is generated. For example, data might be collected from sensors from a particular case study, which needs to be anonymized through particular techniques.</i>
Data sample	<i>If available, a sample of the data for this dataset</i>
Related safety KPI(s)	<i>What project safety KPI(s) the dataset addresses</i>

3.2.1 FAIR DATA

This section describes the principles adopted in EvoRoads to make the data FAIR. Moreover, the section of the EvoRoads metadata profile used to collect FAIR data is described.

Within EvoRoads, **open access** to the data will be provided unless this is contrary to the legitimate interests of the beneficiaries, including commercial exploitation. On top of data openness, EvoRoads will fulfil the FAIR principles [1]. FAIR stands for:

- **Findable:** discoverable with metadata, identifiable, and locatable through a standard identification mechanism.
- **Accessible:** always available and obtainable; even if the data is restricted, the metadata is open. Data can be restricted and still be FAIR, following the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”. So not all data has to be made open. The Open Data Institute (ODI)⁶ defines Open Data as those that anyone can access, use and share. According to the ODI, Open Data must be licensed to make clear that anyone can use the data in any way they want, including transforming, combining, and sharing it with others, even for commercial purposes. On the other hand, Open Data may not be FAIR. For example, publicly available data may lack sufficient documentation to meet the FAIR principles, such as licensing for clear re-use.
- **Interoperable:** both syntactically pursuable and semantically understandable, allowing data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organisations, or countries.

⁶ <https://theodi.org/>

- **Reusable:** sufficiently described and shared with the least restrictive licenses, allowing the widest re-use possible and the least cumbersome integration with other data sources.

Metadata of deposited data will be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent (to the extent legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded), in line with the FAIR principles.

MAKING DATA FINDABLE

Metadata and data should be easy for both humans and computers to find. Machine-readable metadata are essential for the automatic discovery of datasets and services. Data and metadata are assigned to a globally unique and persistent identifier assigned by Cefriel for usage within the project. The published DMP will then be uniquely identified with a DOI by the Argos platform. Moreover, data are described with rich metadata that clearly and explicitly includes the identifier of the data it describes.

A short description of information collected in the section “FAIR DATA - Making data Findable” is reported in Table 5.

Table 5: “FAIR DATA – Making data Findable” section of the EvoRoads metadata profile

FAIR DATA – MAKING DATA FINDABLE	
Search keywords approach	<i>Indicate keywords related to the dataset</i>
Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) (Only for generated data)	<i>Describe here if any versioning approach is used for data and metadata, and how they are traced.</i>

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE

Data and metadata are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol. This principle focuses on retrieving data and metadata from their identifiers. Data retrieval should be mediated without specialised or proprietary tools or communication methods. To maximise data re-use, the protocol should be free (no-cost) and open (-sourced) and thus globally implementable to facilitate data retrieval (e.g., HTTP, FTP, SMTP, etc.). However, where personal data is involved, the protocol must also support authentication and authorisation procedures to ensure privacy and compliance with data protection regulations, such as General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), ensuring secure access and proper handling of sensitive information.

A short description of information collected in the section “FAIR DATA – Making data openly Accessible” is reported in Table 6.

Table 6: “FAIR DATA – Making data openly accessible” section of the EvoRoads metadata profile

FAIR DATA – MAKING DATA OPENLY ACCESSIBLE	
Data openly available	<i>Indicate here if the data are open and free accessible (for example, specify if the protocol is free and open-sourced), or under restrictions, and, in case, specify the restrictions.</i>
Data access requirements	<i>If there are any, specify the restrictions to data access, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions</i>
Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)	<i>Describe how data will be made accessible to project partners.</i>

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MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

Data usually needs to be integrated with other data and to interoperate with applications or workflows for analysis, storage, and processing. Interoperability typically means that each computer system has at least knowledge of the other system's data exchange formats. (Meta)data should use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation and a controlled vocabulary. Data should be readable for machines without requiring specialised or ad hoc algorithms, translators, or mappings. Data should be collected and shared using a standard format for that data type.

A short description of information collected in the section “FAIR DATA – Making data Interoperable” is reported in Table 7.

Table 7: “FAIR DATA – Making interoperable” section of the EvoRoads metadata profile

FAIR DATA – MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE	
Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies	<i>Describe here if any standard or procedures for metadata creation is used, and report them</i>

INCREASE DATA RE-USE

The goal of FAIR is to optimise the re-use of data. To achieve this, metadata and data should be well-described so that they can be replicated and/or combined in different settings. Therefore, (meta)data should be richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes and released with a clear and accessible data usage license. They should be associated with detailed provenance for enhancing data re-use, and, finally, data and metadata should meet domain-relevant community standards: if community standards or best practices for data archiving and sharing exist, they should be followed.

A short description of the information collected in “FAIR DATA Increase data-reuse” is reported in Table 8. While general fields apply to all datasets, specific fields are required only for generated data. These fields include the timing of data availability for re-use, which specifies how long the data will be accessible to others; the data's usability for third parties, ensuring that the dataset is structured and documented in a way that data can be used after the end of the project; and the length of data reusability, which outlines any data-reuse time.

Table 8: “FAIR DATA – Increase data re-use” section of the EvoRoads metadata profile

FAIR DATA – INCREASE DATA RE-USE (THROUGH CLARIFYING LICENSES)	
Timing of data availability for re-use Timing of data availability for re-use (incl. indications on embargo) - <i>(Only for generated data)</i>	<i>Indicate how long the data will be available for re-use (including embargo indications) (incl. indications on embargo) - (Only for generated data)</i>

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FAIR DATA – INCREASE DATA RE-USE (THROUGH CLARIFYING LICENSES)

Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) - (Only for generated data)	<i>Describe here if the data will be available for third parties' usage, after the end of the project</i>
--	---

Restriction to data re-use	<i>Indicate here any limitations or restrictions about data and metadata re-use</i>
----------------------------	---

Quality assurance process	<i>Indicate here if you plan to indicate metrics, KPIs, or any quality assessment process. In case, provide here details</i>
---------------------------	--

Length of time of data reusability - (Only for generated data)	<i>Indicate here any data-reuse time, if it has to be defined</i>
--	---

Data licensing for wide re-use	<i>Specify here the type of data license considered for wide re-use. For example, open license, etc.</i>
--------------------------------	--

3.2.2 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

This section denotes the aspects related to the allocation of resources in terms of costs and data management responsibilities.

The costs of open access to research data are eligible for the EvoRoads GA. The costs of making scientific publications and hosting a project website are included in the EvoRoads budget as eligible costs.

The Scientific and Technical Committee (STC), defined in D6.1 “Project Management Handbook”, will discuss resources for long-term preservation, associated costs and potential value, and how data will be kept beyond the project and for how long.

A short description of the information collected in the section “Allocation of resources” is reported in Table 9.

Table 9: “Allocation of resources” section of the EvoRoads metadata profile

ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

Cost estimates for making data FAIR	<i>Indicate here the estimated cost for applying the above reported FAIR principles and making data FAIR.</i>
-------------------------------------	---

3.2.3 DATA SECURITY

This section refers to the data security aspects of each dataset managed within the EvoRoads project.

Each project party is entitled to adopt its own internal policies and resources to ensure safe and secure data storage. Data storage on a safe and secure server is strongly recommended to guarantee data recovery in case of failure.

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The personnel able to access data shared among the partners involved will be agreed upon among the partners for any project task.

Further data storage repositories such as cloud servers, Github, and Zenodo could be made available for EvoRoads partners in the next months, and data security aspects will be provided for each dataset/data storage.

A short description of the information collected in the section “Data Security” is reported in Table 10.

Table 10: “Data security” section of the EvoRoads metadata profile

DATA SECURITY	
Data security	<i>Describe here information about data security. For example, which servers will host the collected data, who will oversee the servers, who can access such servers, and if periodical backups are planned.</i>
Certified repositories	<i>Indicate what security measures will be implemented to guarantee safe data storage. These security measures should affect the previously indicated 'data storage'</i>

3.2.4 ETHICAL ASPECTS

This section refers to the ethical aspects concerning the data collected and shared within the project. All activities developed within the project will safeguard individuals’ fundamental rights. During the project life cycle, the main pillars of the relevant EU legal framework will be adopted regarding ethical and legal issues.

PROTECTION OF PERSONAL DATA

The right to data protection is enshrined in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union [3], which effectively protects individuals’ right to privacy by giving them control over how information about them is collected and used. EvoRoads will pay attention to research tasks related to collecting and processing personal data (e.g., profiling, data-mining techniques, and big-data analytics) since they may pose higher risks to individuals’ rights regarding data protection.

The GDPR⁷ will be respected for all relevant personal data collected. Proper anonymisation or pseudonymisation techniques will be adopted for each specific dataset that includes personal data.

Anonymisation is one of the best ways to mitigate ethical concerns from using personal data [2]. However, other ethical issues could relate to the origins of the data or how they were obtained. For this reason, the source of the datasets will be clearly identified by EvoRoads to ensure that the anonymisation happens at the point and time at which the data are collected.

When the project involves the partners’ access to personal data, the partners are regarded as responsible for treating said data and shall comply with the rules. The Lead Contact (LC) of each organisation involved in EvoRoads also assumes the role of Data Protection Officer (DPO).

INFORMED CONSENT PROCEDURES

Informed consent entails giving sufficient information about the research and ensuring that there is no explicit or implicit coercion so that participants in the research activities can make an informed and free decision on their possible involvement. The information must be provided in a form that is comprehensible and accessible to participants in a written

⁷ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>

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form, and time should be allowed for the participants to consider their choices and to discuss their decision with others if appropriate. The informed consent must report information on the scope and objectives of the research and must inform participants of their right to refuse to participate or withdraw from the investigation whenever and for whatever reason they wish.

EvoRoads will define and adopt robust informed consent when project activities require the direct involvement of human participants. The informed consent will clearly explain how the data will be collected, used, and stored and when it will be deleted. It will clearly state that EvoRoads adopts the data minimization principle: the project collects the minimum amount of personal data needed to deliver the research activities described in the GA.

A short description of the information collected in the section “Ethical Aspects” of the EvoRoads metadata profile is reported in Table 11.

Table 11: “Ethical Aspects” section of the EvoRoads metadata profile

ETHICAL ASPECTS	
Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing	<i>Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can impact data sharing? Does the dataset contain personal data? Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?</i>

3.2.5 OTHER ISSUES

This section is meant to collect any other relevant information on the usage of other procedures for data management. A short description of the information collected in the section “Other Aspects” is reported in Table 12.

Table 12: “Other Aspects” section of the EvoRoads metadata profile

OTHER ASPECTS	
Other procedures for data management to be specified	<i>Do you, or will you, use other national/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?</i>

3.3 HOW THE DATA CATALOGUE SUPPORTS THE DMP

In contrast to the data catalogue, the DMP is not intended for daily project activities. Instead, it is expected to be published periodically (M8, M18, M36) during the lifetime of the project, providing a snapshot of the data that is being used in the project at those points in time. Furthermore, while the data catalogue is mainly useful internally, the DMP's goal is to be useful also outside of the project, for example, for similar research projects to discover datasets that can be reused or enhanced. While they differ in their goals, the two entities are interconnected throughout the lifecycle of a data source in the EvoRoads project.

The procedures for using a data source depend on whether it already exists and is being reused, or whether it is generated from scratch (see Figure 3). In both cases, the first and fundamental requirement is compliance with ethical and data privacy guidelines described and considered in Chapter 3.2.4. To support this, partners are provided with the ethical

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decision tree⁸ support tool provided by the European Commission (EC). This interactive tool helps quickly determine whether a data source involves personal data, which requires careful handling, and whether ethical concerns arise in its collection or use.

Figure 3: Flowchart showing the appropriate steps to follow for a correct usage of data sources in the project

⁸ <https://ec.europa.eu/assets/rtd/ethics-data-protection-decision-tree/index.html>

If no issues are identified, the data source can be described using the EvoRoadsDCAT-AP profile and published in the data catalogue, where it will be reviewed by the Ethics and Data Management team. If issues are detected, the same team must be consulted to try to solve the issue. In some cases, anonymisation techniques or restricting data collection to a subset that excludes personal data may enable its use. If the issue cannot be resolved, however, the Ethics and Data Management team will prohibit the use of that data source in the project.

For data generated from scratch, if the collection process involves direct interaction with users (e.g. through surveys), partners must provide informed consent and a privacy policy that clearly explains what data will be collected and how it will be processed. Once these requirements are satisfied, the data can be submitted to the data catalogue.

When the data sources are in the data catalogue and have been approved by the Ethics and Data Managers, they can be considered approved for usage in the project. At the appropriate point in time, these same data sources are migrated from the data catalogue to the DMP so that their description can be published. This migration means that data sources described with the EvoRoadsDCAT-AP metadata profile in the data catalogue are then described using the EvoRoads DMP metadata profile in the DMP. Since the two profiles were intentionally designed with significant overlap, the process is straightforward: DMP-specific metadata fields (e.g. those related to FAIR aspects such as search keywords) are integrated either by the partner who published the data source or by the Ethics and Data Managers. Conversely, fields relevant only to the data catalogue but not to the DMP are not transferred. Finally, for metadata fields included in the EvoRoads DMP profile but not in EvoRoadsDCAT-AP, partners were asked to provide the required information where necessary, while project-wide decisions on specific fields were applied consistently.

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4 ETHICS COMPLIANCE: AI-ACT

While the data catalogue and DMP have been used to keep track of potential ethical issues related to the reuse, collection, or use of data in the project's activities, an additional consideration for what AI systems can use such data or how these data can be used in the project has been made necessary by the introduction of the AI Act.

To guarantee the responsible development and use of AI, the European Union has defined the concept of Trustworthy AI based on three fundamental pillars: compliance with existing laws and regulations (Lawful), adherence to fundamental human values (Ethical) and technical security and resilience against risks (Robust). As outlined in the Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI⁹, these principles have been translated into practical requirements, such as transparency, human oversight, data protection, and fairness.

The AI Act is a European regulation that integrates the Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI into a binding regulatory framework, establishing concrete rules, classifying AI-based systems, and imposing stringent requirements for high-risk applications. It introduces a risk-based classification system for AI-based systems, dividing them into four main categories:

- *Unacceptable risk*: Prohibited systems, such as those employing subliminal manipulative techniques or social scoring;
- *High risk*: Applications impacting critical sectors (e.g., healthcare, infrastructure, mobility) that are subject to strict compliance requirements;
- *Limited risk*: Systems that require transparency obligations, such as chatbots or deepfakes;
- *Minimal risk*: Unregulated systems, such as spam filters or AI-powered video games.

The AI Act seeks to balance technological innovation with the protection of fundamental rights, promoting the responsible use of AI. It includes human oversight, data security, and non-discrimination provisions while supporting AI-based research and development in strategic sectors.

EvoRoads Project is committed to fully complying with the EU AI Act, its core principles, and the Trustworthy AI criteria, ensuring that all developed AI-based technologies are lawful, ethical, robust, and respectful of human rights and values.

The EvoRoads project involves multiple entities, meaning any subject (company, individual, or public body) engaged in developing, distributing, or using an AI-based system. Depending on their role, each entity has specific obligations and responsibilities to ensure compliance with European AI regulations. The key entities involved in the EvoRoads Project include:

- **Provider**: A company, public entity, or individual that develops an AI-based system or a general-purpose AI model and places it on the market or into service under its own name or brand;
- **Deployer**: Any entity using an AI system under its authority (e.g., companies, public bodies), except for personal, non-professional use.

To correctly classify the role of each EvoRoads beneficiary and the characteristics of the AI-based systems being developed, used, or distributed, the project will leverage the EU AI Act Compliance Checker¹⁰. By answering a series of questions, this tool will support EvoRoads beneficiaries in identifying the risk level of EvoRoads AI-based system and

9 <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>

10 <https://artificialintelligenceact.eu/assessment/eu-ai-act-compliance-checker/>

being informed about specific articles of the AI Act to be considered as fully compliant with trustworthy AI principles. The results provided by the tool will be documented in project deliverables dedicated to the EvoRoads AI-based solutions.

By leveraging the EU AI Act Compliance Checker, the EvoRoads project will ensure full compliance with European AI regulations, fostering the development and adoption of safe, ethical, and reliable AI-based systems in road transport.

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5 CONCLUSIONS

In the second release of the EvoRoads DMP, the project presents its refined approach to data management, building on the foundations of the first version. This release introduces the EvoRoadsDCAT-AP metadata profile, used in the project's data catalogue, and provides a detailed overview of the overall data management and ethics framework. It also outlines the process for handling dataset descriptions: datasets are first described according to the EvoRoadsDCAT-AP profile and submitted to the data catalogue, where the Ethics and Data Management team reviews them for quality and compliance with ethical standards. Once approved, the dataset descriptions are migrated to the DMP on the Argos platform, where they are described following the EvoRoads DMP metadata profile.

In addition, to ensure compliance with the EU AI Act, partners developing AI systems assess their solutions using the Act's framework. These assessments are reviewed by the Ethics and Data Management team, and compliant systems are approved for use and documented in the relevant project deliverables, accompanied by an AI Act compliance notice.

Overall, the DMP serves as a strategic roadmap for responsible and ethical data management, establishing the basis for effective collaboration, innovation, and knowledge exchange within the research community. The EvoRoads project remains committed to cultivating a culture of openness, transparency, and accountability in the handling of research data, while safeguarding privacy in relation to the pilot studies conducted within the project.

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7 ANNEX

ANNEX I – COLLECTED DATASETS

EvoRoads DMP v2

Version 1

Description

Second version of the collected datasets descriptions used or intended to be used in the EvoRoads EU Project

Funder

European Commission | EC

Grant

Horizon Europe

Researchers

Marco Grassi (0000-0003-3139-3049), Alice Pamio (0009-0005-1089-5148), Marco Comerio (0000-0003-3494-9516)

Organizations

CEFRIEL

LICENSE: not specified DOI: - 22/10/2025

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1. Main Info

Title of DMP: EvoRoads DMP v2

Description:

Second version of the collected datasets descriptions used or intended to be used in the EvoRoads EU Project

Researchers:

Marco Grassi (0000-0003-3139-3049)

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Organizations:

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission | EC

Grants: Horizon Europe

Project: EvoRoads

3. License

License: notspecified

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

1 - Connected vehicle data

Data from vehicles through 5G network

Data Management Plan | EvoRoads DMP v2 LICENSE: notspecified DOI: - 22/10/2025

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Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

1

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

Infrastructure

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

- Vehicle sensor data
- Connectivity network data

1.1.4 Partners

INDRA

1.1.5 Workstream

T4.2

1.1.6 Work packages

WP4

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

Receiving information from vehicles via 5G. Metrics on received data volumes and upload speeds

1.1.8 Schema of the data

CAM, DENM, CPM

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1.1.9 Format of the data

ASN.1 UPER JSON

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

N/A

1.1.12 Reused data

No

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

Data from vehicles of an OEM, and provided by them

1.1.14 Size

N/A

1.1.17 Data storage

N/A

N/A

1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

N/A

2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

Unknown

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

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N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

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4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

No

The vehicle data is anonymous

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

No

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2 - Alicante Public Buses Dataset

Road status data: Data from on-board sensors regarding accelerometers, etc.

Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

2 - Alicante Public Buses Dataset

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

Vehicle

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

Vehicle sensor data

1.1.4 Partners

INDRA

1.1.5 Workstream

T4.2

1.1.6 Work packages

WP4

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

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Vehicle vibration values that allow road conditions to be extrapolated and the areas with the most defects to be identified

1.1.8 Schema of the data

Custom

1.1.9 Format of the data

JSON, XML, CSV

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

N/A

1.1.12 Reused data

No

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

Data filtering to remove noise and extreme outliers.

1.1.14 Size

N/A

1.1.16 Dataset license

N/A

1.1.17 Data storage

N/A

N/A

1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

N/A

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2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

Unknown

N/A

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

N/A

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2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

No

The vehicle data is anonymous

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

No

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3 - GIS | Digital Twin visualization

Road Infrastructure Digital twin data: Platform visualization of data over a Digital Twin of the road

Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

3 - GIS | Digital Twin visualization

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

Infrastructure

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

Road defects data

1.1.4 Partners

INDRA

1.1.5 Workstream

T4.2

1.1.6 Work packages

WP4

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

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Near real-time knowledge of road conditions for a specific section of road

1.1.8 Schema of the data

N/A

1.1.9 Format of the data

N/A

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

N/A

1.1.12 Reused data

N/A

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

Visual representation of the road status through 2D/3D GIS based model

1.1.14 Size

N/A

1.1.15 Dataset metadata licence

N/A

1.1.16 Dataset license

N/A

1.1.17 Data storage

N/A

N/A

1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

N/A

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2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

Unknown

N/A

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

N/A

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2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

No

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

No

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4 - Probe Vehicle Road Condition Dataset

Data from a probe vehicle with OBU: contains data from GNSS receiver, IMU and AI detection of pothole from a video feed (video not shared)

Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

4 - Probe Vehicle Road Condition Dataset

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

Infrastructure

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

- Vehicle sensor data
- Asset management and road maintenance data

1.1.4 Partners

- Federico Princiotto (0000-0001-8183-4469)
- Daniele Brevi (0000-0003-4549-7906)

1.1.5 Workstream

T4.3

1.1.6 Work packages

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WP4

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

The probe vehicle can detect various information about the roads status. At the moment, the main usage is pothole detection and damages signals detection.

1.1.8 Schema of the data

N/A

1.1.9 Format of the data

N/A

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

Road and Signage Maintenance Level (Detection of road defects)

1.1.12 Reused data

NO

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

The probe vehicle can detect various information about the roads status. Specific sensor and objectives to be defined with the Italian Pilot Partners.

1.1.14 Size

N/A

1.1.15 Dataset metadata licence

N/A

1.1.16 Dataset license

N/A

1.1.17 Data storage

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N/A

N/A

1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

N/A

2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

Unknown

N/A

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

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2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

No

Okay sharing in the consortium, but there could be issues sharing the gps position outside the consortium.

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

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No

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5 - Tracking of road actors in the Corso Spezia and Via Maroncelli intersection

Data from one Road Side Unit (RSU)

Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

5 - Tracking of road actors in the Corso Spezia and Via Maroncelli intersection

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

- VRU
- Vehicle

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

- Road user behavioural data
- Road traffic data

1.1.4 Partners

- Federico Princiotto (0000-0001-8183-4469)
- Daniele Brevi (0000-0003-4549-7906)

1.1.5 Workstream

T4.3

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1.1.6 Work packages

WP4

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

The RSUs will monitor the intersections and generate live messages listing all the road actor detected and their positions. This data could be further elaborated to computed speeds and trajectories to estimate the user behaviour.

1.1.8 Schema of the data

CPM

1.1.9 Format of the data

JSON

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

Use of Crosswalk (Share of pedestrians using designated crosswalk vs. crossing elsewhere)

1.1.12 Reused data

NO

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

Process camera and lidar data to generate CPM messages.

1.1.14 Size

N/A

1.1.15 Dataset metadata licence

N/A

1.1.16 Dataset license

N/A

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1.1.17 Data storage

N/A

N/A

1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

N/A

2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

Unknown

N/A

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

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N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

No

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

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No

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7 - Road Accident dataset (no. injured or dead persons, time, position, etc.), available from 2000.

Road Accident dataset (no. injured or dead persons, time, position, etc.), available from 2000.

Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

7 - Road Accident dataset (no. injured or dead persons, time, position, etc.), available from 2000.

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

Traffic

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

Road accident data

1.1.4 Partners

CSI

1.1.5 Workstream

• T2.2

• T2.3

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• T4.3

1.1.6 Work packages

WP4

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

Historical DB of road accident, that could be used to look for correlation between safety KPI and actual accidente severity/frequency.

1.1.8 Schema of the data

N/A

1.1.9 Format of the data

JSON, CSV, XML

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

Road risk per road segment (based on #accidents,length and flow)

1.1.12 Reused data

NO

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

N/A

1.1.14 Size

N/A

1.1.15 Dataset metadata licence

Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike 4.0

1.1.16 Dataset license

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1.1.17 Data storage

N/A

N/A

1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

N/A

2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

Unknown

N/A

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

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N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

No

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

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8 - Road traffic data (avg. daily traffic flow, link to the regional road graph) available from 2014 to 2022;

Road traffic data (avg. daily traffic flow, link to the regional road graph) available from 2014 to 2022;

Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

8 - Road traffic data (avg. daily traffic flow, link to the regional road graph) available from 2014 to 2022;

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

Traffic

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

Road traffic data

1.1.4 Partners

CSI2

1.1.5 Workstream

• T2.2

• T2.3

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• T4.3

1.1.6 Work packages

WP4

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

Historical DB of road traffic flow, that could be used to look for correlation between traffic and actual accidents severity/frequency.

1.1.8 Schema of the data

N/A

1.1.9 Format of the data

JSON, CSV, XML

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

Road risk per road segment (based on #accidents,length and flow)

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

NO

1.1.14 Size

N/A

1.1.15 Dataset metadata licence

Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike 4.0

1.1.16 Dataset license

Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike 4.0

1.1.17 Data storage

N/A

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N/A

1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

N/A

2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

Unknown

N/A

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

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N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

No

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

No

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9 - Road Graph and Topographic database, available at a scale of 1:5000.

Road Graph and Topographic database, available at a scale of 1:5000.

Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

9 - Road Graph and Topographic database, available at a scale of 1:5000.

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

Infrastructure

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

Road infrastructure data

1.1.4 Partners

CSI3

1.1.5 Workstream

T4.3

1.1.6 Work packages

WP4

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

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Road infrastructure features as foundation layer for the analysis

1.1.8 Schema of the data

N/A

1.1.9 Format of the data

N/A

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

Road risk per road segment (based on #accidents,length and flow)

1.1.12 Reused data

NO

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

N/A

1.1.14 Size

N/A

1.1.15 Dataset metadata licence

Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike 4.0

1.1.16 Dataset license

Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike 4.0

1.1.17 Data storage

N/A

N/A

1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

N/A

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2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

Unknown

N/A

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

N/A

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2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

No

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

No

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10 - Event data set (results locally on the e-scooter sensor kit)

The data set of each pothole contains the pothole's area and image resolution, as well as GPS coordinates of the micromobility vehicle's location.

Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

10 - Event data set (results locally on the e-scooter sensor kit)

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

Infrastructure

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

Road infrastructure data

1.1.4 Partners

RIGA

1.1.5 Workstream

T4.4

1.1.6 Work packages

WP4

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

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The kit collects data from camera (AI driven detection of road quality)

1.1.8 Schema of the data

Custom

1.1.9 Format of the data

CSV

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

N/A

1.1.12 Reused data

NO

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

N/A

1.1.14 Size

20 MB

1.1.15 Dataset metadata licence

Other (Not Open)

1.1.16 Dataset license

Other (Not Open)

1.1.17 Data storage

N/A

N/A

1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

N/A

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2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

Unknown

N/A

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

N/A

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2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

Yes

If a photograph is captured in a manner that does not comply with guideline, it may constitute a violation of personal data regulations

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

No

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11 - Route and sensors data set (results locally on the e-scooter sensor kit)

Route and sensors data set (results locally on the e-scooter sensor kit)

Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

11 - Route and sensors data set (results locally on the e-scooter sensor kit)

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

- Vehicle
- Infrastructure

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

Road infrastructure data

1.1.4 Partners

RIGA

1.1.5 Workstream

T4.4

1.1.6 Work packages

WP4

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1.1.7 Purpose of the data

The kit collects data from sensors

1.1.8 Schema of the data

Custom

1.1.9 Format of the data

CSV

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

N/A

1.1.12 Reused data

NO

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

N/A

1.1.14 Size

20 MB

1.1.15 Dataset metadata licence

N/A

1.1.16 Dataset licence

N/A

N/A

1.1.17 Data storage

N/A

N/A

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1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

N/A

2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

Unknown

N/A

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/AN/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

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2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

No

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

No

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19 - Video streams from drones

video streams from drones

Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

19

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

- Traffic
- Infrastructure

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

Road infrastructure data

1.1.4 Partners

BEIA

1.1.5 Workstream

T2.2

1.1.6 Work packages

WP2

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

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Provide information to be incorporated into the databases

1.1.8 Schema of the data

N/A

1.1.9 Format of the data

N/A

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

N/A

1.1.12 Reused data

N/A

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

N/A

1.1.14 Size

N/A

1.1.15 Dataset metadata licence

N/A

1.1.16 Dataset license

N/A

1.1.17 Data storage

N/A

N/A

1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

N/A

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2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

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N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

N/A

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

No

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20 - Satellite images

Satellite images

Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

20

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

Other

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

Other

1.1.4 Partners

BEIA

1.1.5 Workstream

T2.2

1.1.6 Work packages

WP2

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

Provide images that are used by the AI algorithms

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1.1.8 Schema of the data

N/A

1.1.9 Format of the data

N/A

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

N/A

1.1.12 Reused data

N/A

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

N/A

1.1.14 Size

N/A

1.1.15 Dataset metadata licence

N/A

1.1.16 Dataset license

N/A

1.1.17 Data storage

N/A

N/A

1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

N/A

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2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

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N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

N/A

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

No

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21 - Vehicles sensing data

Vehicles sensing data

Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

20

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

Other

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

Vehicle sensor data

1.1.4 Partners

BEIA

1.1.5 Workstream

T4.5

1.1.6 Work packages

WP4

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

Object detection, lane markings, road signs, pedestrians, distance to obstacles

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1.1.8 Schema of the data

N/A

1.1.9 Format of the data

N/A

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

N/A

1.1.12 Reused data

N/A

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

N/A

1.1.14 Size

N/A

1.1.15 Dataset metadata licence

N/A

1.1.16 Dataset license

N/A

1.1.17 Data storage

N/A

N/A

1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

N/A

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2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

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N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

N/A

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

No

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22 - Data from Roadside Units

Data from Roadside Units

Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

20

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

Other

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

Road traffic data

1.1.4 Partners

BEIA

1.1.5 Workstream

T4.5

1.1.6 Work packages

WP4

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

Road surface condition, light signals, lane closures

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1.1.8 Schema of the data

N/A

1.1.9 Format of the data

N/A

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

N/A

1.1.12 Reused data

N/A

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

N/A

1.1.14 Size

N/A

1.1.15 Dataset metadata licence

N/A

1.1.16 Dataset license

N/A

1.1.17 Data storage

N/A

N/A

1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

N/A

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2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

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N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

N/A

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

No

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23 - Data base of traffic accidents (monitoring tool of the City of Alba Iulia)

Data base of traffic accidents (monitoring tool of the City of Alba Iulia)

Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

23

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

Other

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

Other

1.1.4 Partners

BEIA

1.1.5 Workstream

T4.5

1.1.6 Work packages

WP4

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

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Using data for a helpdesk solution

1.1.8 Schema of the data

N/A

1.1.9 Format of the data

N/A

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

N/A

1.1.12 Reused data

N/A

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

N/A

1.1.14 Size

N/A

1.1.15 Dataset metadata licence

N/A

1.1.16 Dataset license

N/A

1.1.17 Data storage

N/A

N/A

1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

N/A

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2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

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N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

N/A

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

No

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24 - Road defects and their classification index

Road defects and their classification index

Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

24

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

Other

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

Other

1.1.4 Partners

BEIA

1.1.5 Workstream

T2.2

1.1.6 Work packages

WP2

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

Surface distress - cracks, potholes

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1.1.8 Schema of the data

N/A

1.1.9 Format of the data

N/A

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

N/A

1.1.12 Reused data

N/A

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

N/A

1.1.14 Size

N/A

1.1.15 Dataset metadata licence

N/A

1.1.16 Dataset license

N/A

1.1.17 Data storage

N/A

N/A

1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

N/A

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2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

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N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

N/A

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

No

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25 - Fixed road infrastructure data

Fixed road infrastructure data

Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

25

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

Other

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

Other

1.1.4 Partners

BEIA

1.1.5 Workstream

T4.5

1.1.6 Work packages

WP4

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

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Tracks road surface conditions for predictive maintenance and also provides an inventory of road assets

1.1.8 Schema of the data

N/A

1.1.9 Format of the data

N/A

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

N/A

1.1.12 Reused data

N/A

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

N/A

1.1.14 Size

N/A

1.1.17 Data storage

N/A

N/A

1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

N/A

2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

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N/A

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

N/A

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3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

N/A

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

No

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26 - Road user behavioural data

Road user behavioural data

Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

26

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

Other

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

Roadside units data

1.1.4 Partners

BEIA

1.1.5 Workstream

T4.5

1.1.6 Work packages

WP4

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

Traffic flow patterns: congestion levels, peak travel times

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1.1.8 Schema of the data

N/A

1.1.9 Format of the data

N/A

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

N/A

1.1.12 Reused data

N/A

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

N/A

1.1.14 Size

N/A

1.1.15 Dataset metadata licence

N/A

1.1.16 Dataset license

N/A

1.1.17 Data storage

N/A

N/A

1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

N/A

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2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

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N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

N/A

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

No

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27 - Road Infrastructure Digital twin data

Road Infrastructure Digital twin data

Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

277

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

Other

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

Road infrastructure data

1.1.4 Partners

BEIA

1.1.5 Workstream

T4.5

1.1.6 Work packages

WP4

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

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Monitoring road conditions in real time. Predictive maintenance - detecting cracks, potholes

1.1.8 Schema of the data

N/A

1.1.9 Format of the data

N/A

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

N/A

1.1.12 Reused data

N/A

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

N/A

1.1.14 Size

N/A

1.1.15 Dataset metadata licence

N/A

1.1.16 Dataset license

N/A

1.1.17 Data storage

N/A

N/A

1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

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N/A

2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

N/A

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2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

N/A

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

No

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28 - 2D Visual Data

Road safety and infrastructure condition data

Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

28

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

- Traffic
- Infrastructure

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

Road infrastructure data

1.1.4 Partners

UCY

1.1.5 Workstream

T2.2

1.1.6 Work packages

WP2

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

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Infrastructure monitoring

1.1.8 Schema of the data

N/A

1.1.9 Format of the data

JPEG, PNG, MP4

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

N/A

1.1.12 Reused data

NO

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

footage capture from drone camera

1.1.14 Size

1-100s GB

1.1.15 Dataset metadata licence

CC_BY_4_0

1.1.16 Dataset license

CC-BY

1.1.17 Data storage

N/A

N/A

1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

N/A

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2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

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N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

Visible number plates or people faces

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

No

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29 - Crowdsources Road damages

Road safety and infrastructure condition data

Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

29

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

- Safety
- Infrastructure

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

- Crowdsourcing data
- Roadside units data
- Road infrastructure data
- Road defects data

1.1.4 Partners

UCY

1.1.5 Workstream

- T2.1

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- T4.1

- T4.4

- T4.5

1.1.6 Work packages

WP2

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

Infrastructure monitoring for safety reasons

1.1.9 Format of the data

JPEG,PNG,MP4

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

N/A

1.1.12 Reused data

NO

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

footage capture from smartphone camera

1.1.14 Size

N/A

1.1.15 Dataset metadata licence

CC_BY_4_0

1.1.16 Dataset licence

N/A

1.1.17 Data storage

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N/A

N/A

1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

N/A

2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

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N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

Visible number plates or people faces

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

No

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31 - General road status

Connected vehicle data: Data from EDGE to Vehicles via 5G

Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

31

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

Vehicle

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

Road defects data

1.1.4 Partners

- Raul Villalba
- Djemre Ozmendji

1.1.5 Workstream

T4.2

1.1.6 Work packages

WP4

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

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Receiving information from the infrastructure via 5G to warn the vehicles/drivers

1.1.8 Schema of the data

DATEX II

1.1.9 Format of the data

XML

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

IDIADA pilot KPIs

1.1.12 Reused data

NO

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

Process infrastructure sensors' data and generate the C-ITS messages accordingly

1.1.14 Size

N/A

1.1.15 Dataset metadata licence

N/A

1.1.16 Dataset license

N/A

1.1.17 Data storage

N/A

N/A

1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

N/A

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2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/AN/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

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N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

Confidential data

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

No

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33 - Env_Sensor.db roadStatus.db AtmRoad_info.db transito.db Asphalt_temp.db Camera.db

Environmental conditions (Temperature & Humidity), asphalt Temperature, Fog condition, Object detections informations vehicles related to the road line location, information about if the road is obstructed or not

Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

33

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

Connectivity

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

Road defects data

1.1.4 Partners

- Jesus David Coral
- Arcadi Castanyer

1.1.5 Workstream

T2.4

1.1.6 Work packages

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WP2

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

Producing information of the environmental and road condition

1.1.8 Schema of the data

Proprietary

1.1.9 Format of the data

InnoDB

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

IDIADA pilot KPIs

1.1.12 Reused data

NO

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

Data collected from sensor. Temperature sensor Humidity sensor Ultrasonic sensor Camera sensor Luminosity sensor Infrared sensor

1.1.14 Size

1 - 5 GB

1.1.15 Dataset metadata licence

GPL

1.1.16 Dataset license

N/A

1.1.17 Data storage

N/A

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N/A

1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

N/A

2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

No

N/A

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

2025

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

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N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

NO

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

No

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34 - Sentinel-1

Sentinel-1 provides all-weather, day and night radar imagery for land and ocean services. EO Browser provides data acquired in Interferometric Wide Swath (IW) and Extra Wide Swath (EW) modes processed to Level-1 Ground Range Detected (GRD).

Template: [EvoRoads Template](#)

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

34

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

Infrastructure

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

Other

1.1.4 Partners

- Konstantinos N. Christidis
- Angelina Despotopoulou

1.1.5 Workstream

T2.2

1.1.6 Work packages

WP2

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

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Detection of defects and pavement deterioration using InSAR

1.1.8 Schema of the data

Other

1.1.9 Format of the data

>5TB

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

N/A

1.1.12 Reused data

YES

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

Data collected via Satellite and made available through Copernicus Browser

1.1.14 Size

>5TB

1.1.15 Dataset metadata licence

Copernicus Sentinel Data Licence

1.1.16 Dataset license

Copernicus Sentinel Data Licence

1.1.17 Data storage

Copernicus Browser

N/A

1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

N/A

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2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

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N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

N/A

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

No

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35 - Road Damage Dataset

Collection of road damages with different categories e.g: longitudinal crack, transversal crack, alligator crack, potholes, manholes. Dataset used to train the algorithms.

Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

35

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

Infrastructure

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

Vehicle sensor data

1.1.4 Partners

DTU

1.1.5 Workstream

T3.4

1.1.6 Work packages

WP3

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

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Road Condition Assessment based on frequency and density distribution.

1.1.8 Schema of the data

N/A

1.1.9 Format of the data

N/A

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

N/A

1.1.12 Reused data

YES

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

N/A

1.1.14 Size

N/A

1.1.15 Dataset metadata licence

N/A

1.1.16 Dataset license

N/A

N/A

1.1.17 Data storage

N/A

N/A

1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

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N/A

2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

Unknown

N/A

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

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N/A

2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

No

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

No

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36 - Vibration Data (Raw)

Collection of raw accelerometer and GPS signals recorded on Copenhagen roads using sensors. Dataset used to develop features for IRI estimation and road roughness classification.

Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

36

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

Infrastructure

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

Vehicle sensor data

1.1.4 Partners

DTU

1.1.5 Workstream

T2.3

1.1.6 Work packages

WP2

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

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Input signals for predictive maintenance models; baseline data for deriving IRI and supporting feature extraction.

1.1.8 Schema of the data

Custom

1.1.9 Format of the data

CSV

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

N/A

1.1.12 Reused data

YES

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

N/A

1.1.14 Size

5 GB

1.1.16 Dataset license

N/A

N/A

1.1.17 Data storage

Internal DTU SharePoint

Internal DTU SharePoint

1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

N/A

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2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

Unknown

N/A

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

N/A

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2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

No

6 Other Aspects

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37 - Swedish road data (NVDB)

Open road data from the Swedish national road database NVDB

Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

37

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

Infrastructure

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

- Road infrastructure data
- Road defects data

1.1.4 Partners

VTI

1.1.5 Workstream

T1.3

1.1.6 Work packages

WP1

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

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Analysis presented in D1.3

1.1.8 Schema of the data

Other

1.1.9 Format of the data

GDB

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

KPI #1: SLIPPERY ROADS

KPI #2: DISTRESS AND DETERIORATION OF INFRASTRUCTURE

KPI #3: SPEED COMPLIANCE IN RELATION TO PERFORMANCE OF COMMUNICATING SPEED LIMITS (CAV'S REDINESS)

1.1.12 Reused data

YES

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

N/A

1.1.14 Size

2 GB

1.1.15 Dataset metadata licence

License Not Specified

1.1.16 Dataset license

License Not Specified

1.1.17 Data storage

N/A

N/A

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1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

N/A

2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

Unknown

N/A

2.1.3 Data openly available

NO

2.1.4 Data access requirements

Data accessible for VTI only

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

No plans to share the data in the EvoRoads consortium

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

N/A

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2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

No

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

No

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38 - Swedish road data (PMSV4)

Open road surface data from the Swedish national road surface database PMSV4

Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

38

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

Infrastructure

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

- Road infrastructure data
- Road defects data

1.1.4 Partners

VTI

1.1.5 Workstream

T1.3

1.1.6 Work packages

WP1

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

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Analysis presented in D1.3

1.1.8 Schema of the data

Other

1.1.9 Format of the data

GDB

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

KPI #1: SLIPPERY ROADS

KPI #2: DISTRESS AND DETERIORATION OF INFRASTRUCTURE

KPI #3: SPEED COMPLIANCE IN RELATION TO PERFORMANCE OF COMMUNICATING SPEED LIMITS (CAV'S REDINESS)

1.1.12 Reused data

YES

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

N/A

1.1.14 Size

500 MB

1.1.15 Dataset metadata licence

License Not Specified

1.1.16 Dataset license

License Not Specified

1.1.17 Data storage

N/A

N/A

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1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

N/A

2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

Unknown

N/A

2.1.3 Data openly available

NO

2.1.4 Data access requirements

Data employed and usable by VTI Only

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

Data is not intended to be shared in the EvoRoads Consortium

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

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2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

No

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

No

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39 - Swedish crash data (Strada)

Road crash data from the Swedish national crash database Strada. Data is generally restricted but VTI has direct access as an government agency

Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

39

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

Safety

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

Road accident data

1.1.4 Partners

VTI

1.1.5 Workstream

T1.3

1.1.6 Work packages

WP1

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

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Analysis presented in D1.3

1.1.8 Schema of the data

Other

1.1.9 Format of the data

XLSX

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

KPI #1: SLIPPERY ROADS

KPI #2: DISTRESS AND DETERIORATION OF INFRASTRUCTURE

KPI #3: SPEED COMPLIANCE IN RELATION TO PERFORMANCE OF COMMUNICATING SPEED LIMITS (CAV'S REDINESS)

1.1.12 Reused data

YES

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

N/A

1.1.14 Size

100 MB

1.1.15 Dataset metadata licence

License Not Specified

1.1.16 Dataset licence

License Not Specified

1.1.17 Data storage

N/A

N/A

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1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

N/A

2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

Unknown

N/A

2.1.3 Data openly available

Restricted, sensitive personal data, cannot be shared within EvoRoads

2.1.4 Data access requirements

Cannot be shared within EvoRoads

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

Cannot be shared within EvoRoads

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

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2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

Yes

Restricted, sensitive personal data, cannot be shared within EvoRoads

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

No

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40 - Turin risk per road segments

Road Accident dataset with additional risk quantification column

Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

40

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

Traffic

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

Road accident data

1.1.4 Partners

- Stathis Antoniou (0000-0002-0668-1180)
- Asimina Mertzani (0000-0002-6084-9212)

1.1.5 Workstream

- T2.2
- T2.3

1.1.6 Work packages

WP4

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1.1.7 Purpose of the data

Predicting riskier road segments

1.1.8 Schema of the data

DATEX II

1.1.9 Format of the data

XML

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

Road risk per road segment (based on #accidents,length and flow)

1.1.12 Reused data

NO

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

N/A

1.1.14 Size

15 - 80 MB

1.1.15 Dataset metadata licence

Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike 4.0

1.1.16 Dataset license

Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike 4.0

1.1.17 Data storage

N/A

N/A

1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

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N/A

2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

Unknown

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

N/A

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2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

No

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

No

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41 - Raw Connectivity Logs

Raw data collected by OBUs (latency, bandwidth, service continuity, packet loss...) in proprietary format, including timestamp and geolocation.

Template: [EvoRoads Template](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

41

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

- Infrastructure
- Connectivity

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

- Vehicle sensor data
- Connectivity network data

1.1.4 Partners

Aitor González

1.1.5 Workstream

T4.2

1.1.6 Work packages

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WP4

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

Basis for cleaning, validation, and preliminary analysis.

1.1.8 Schema of the data

CUSTOM

1.1.9 Format of the data

JSON

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

Transmission reliability, network coverage.

1.1.12 Reused data

NO

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

Generated through OBU

1.1.14 Size

N/A

1.1.15 Dataset metadata licence

License Not Specified

1.1.16 Dataset licence

License Not Specified

1.1.17 Data storage

N/A

N/A

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1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

N/A

2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

Unknown

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

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N/A

2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

Yes

GDPR compliance and anonymization of geolocation data

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

No

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42 - Validated Connectivity Dataset

Refined dataset after offline cleaning and validation, aggregated spatio-temporally to remove inconsistencies and normalize parameters.

Template: [EvoRoads Template](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

42

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

- Infrastructure
- Connectivity

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

- Vehicle sensor data
- Connectivity network data

1.1.4 Partners

Aitor González

1.1.5 Workstream

T4.2

1.1.6 Work packages

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WP4

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

Input for the construction of the heat map.

1.1.8 Schema of the data

Custom

1.1.9 Format of the data

CSV

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

Transmission reliability, network coverage.

1.1.12 Reused data

YES

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

Dataset 41 Processed in centralized CTAG servers

1.1.14 Size

N/A

1.1.15 Dataset metadata licence

License Not Specified

1.1.16 Dataset licence

License Not Specified

1.1.17 Data storage

N/A

N/A

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1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

N/A

2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

Unknown

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

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N/A

2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

Yes

GDPR compliance and anonymization of geolocation data.

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

No

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43 - Connectivity Heat Maps

Heat maps showing latency, bandwidth, ... and service continuity across the analyzed road segments.

Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

43

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

- Infrastructure
- Connectivity

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

- Vehicle sensor data
- Connectivity network data

1.1.4 Partners

Aitor González

1.1.5 Workstream

T4.2

1.1.6 Work packages

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WP4

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

Main tool for identifying connectivity-critical areas.

1.1.8 Schema of the data

GEOJSON

1.1.9 Format of the data

GEOJSON, HTML

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

Transmission reliability, network coverage.

1.1.12 Reused data

YES

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

Generated using dataset 42

1.1.14 Size

N/A

1.1.15 Dataset metadata licence

License Not Specified

1.1.16 Dataset licence

License Not Specified

1.1.17 Data storage

N/A

N/A

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1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

N/A

2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

Unknown

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

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N/A

2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

No

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

No

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44 - ISAD-Level Road Classification Map

Classification of road segments according to ISAD levels and V2X services potentially supported, overlaid on the connectivity map.

Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

44

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

- Infrastructure
- Connectivity

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

Other

1.1.4 Partners

Aitor González

1.1.5 Workstream

T4.2

1.1.6 Work packages

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1.1.7 Purpose of the data

Identification of CCAM feasibility and infrastructure improvement needs.

1.1.8 Schema of the data

GeoJSON

1.1.9 Format of the data

GeoJSON, HTML

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

Communication reliability for V2X, service availability.

1.1.12 Reused data

YES, dataset 43

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

Generated from dataset 43

1.1.14 Size

N/A

1.1.15 Dataset metadata licence

License Not Specified

1.1.16 Dataset licence

License Not Specified

1.1.17 Data storage

N/A

N/A

1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

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N/A

2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

Unknown

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

N/A

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2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

No

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

No

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45 - Tracking of road actors in the Corso Galileo Ferraris.

Detection from 2 cameras

Template: EvoRoads Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Dataset id

45

other

1.1.2 Category (Type of output)

- VRU
- Vehicle

1.1.3 Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)

- Road user behavioural data
- Road traffic data

1.1.4 Partners

- Federico Princiotta (0000-0001-8183-4469)
- Daniele Brevi (0000-0003-4549-7906)

1.1.5 Workstream

T4.3

1.1.6 Work packages

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WP4

1.1.7 Purpose of the data

Monitor the intersections and generate live messages listing all the road actor detected and their positions. Use this to alert the approaching vehicles with the number of pedestrians waiting to cross. Monitor also the behaviour of vehicles before and after the alter.

1.1.8 Schema of the data

N/A

1.1.9 Format of the data

N/A

1.1.10 Data sample

N/A

1.1.11 Related safety KPI(s)

Signs Activated for Speed Calming, Speed Compliance, Variance of Traffic Speed, Pedestrian/Cyclist Waiting Time at Crossings

1.1.12 Reused data

NO

1.1.13 Data creation process [generated data only]

Process camera video to generate CPM messages.

1.1.14 Size

N/A

1.1.15 Dataset metadata licence

Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike 4.0

1.1.16 Dataset license

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1.1.17 Data storage

N/A

N/A

1.1.18 Data value (long term) [generated data only]

N/A

2 Fair Aspects

2.1 Fair Aspects

2.1.2 Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) [generated data only]

Unknown

2.1.3 Data openly available

N/A

2.1.4 Data access requirements

N/A

2.1.5 Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)

N/A

2.1.6 Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies

N/A

2.1.7 Timing of data availability for reuse (incl. indications on embargo) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.8 Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.9 Restriction to data re-use

N/A

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2.1.10 Quality assurance process

N/A

2.1.11 Length of time of data reusability [generated data only]

N/A

2.1.12 Data licensing for wide reuse

N/A

3 Allocation of the Resources

3.1 Allocation of the Resources

3.1.1 Cost estimates for making data FAIR

N/A

N/A

4 Data Security

4.1 Data Security

4.1.1 Data security

N/A

4.1.2 Certified repositories

N/A

5 Ethical Aspects

5.1 Ethical Aspects

5.1.1 Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing

No

6 Other Aspects

6.1 Other Aspects

6.1.1 Other procedures for data management to be specified

No

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